

DYNAMICS OF INCREASING SOCIAL-POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation: the next day of our country, it is our important tasks to transform the fate and future of the country into a decisive great force by creating favorable conditions for the spiritual and social support of young people, considered a resource of spiritual potential, which will cause changes in society, bring creative ideas to life. The article reflects on the dynamics of increasing the socio-political activity of young people in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: youth, idea, progress, activity, future, potential, organization, spirituality.

Increasing youth activity is an important factor in the development of our country. A significant part of the population of Uzbekistan consists of young people, which serve as a guarantee of ensuring the great future of the country. The huge potential of Uzbekistan is clearly manifested in the image of young people who are entering social life, have mastered the secrets of modern knowledge and professions, are becoming a decisive force today. The next day of our country, it is our important tasks for each of us to transform them into a huge force that will cause changes in society, bring the ideas of creativity to life, by providing spiritual and social support for young people who are considered a resource of spiritual potential, creating favorable conditions for their worthy place in society.

The political institutionalization of young people leads to the organization of the interests of this socio - demographic group, gives the younger generation the quality of the subject of political relations. The experience gained in youth associations and organizations serves to form a reserve of young political leaders and qualified managers.

As noted in the "UN Youth Strategy", "the most valuable and extremely important resources are embodied in the youth of young people, it is worth investing in it as much as possible, because these investments will return several times more" I fully agree with this extremely important idea.

We see in the youth of young people the meaning of our life, the main effect of our life. We will build the new Uzbekistan together with the young people of azmu shijaat!

In our development strategy, it is one of our top priorities to educate boys and girls who are harmoniously developed in all respects, free-thinking, loyal to the motherland, with strict life views.

In order to systematically and systematically implement the state policy on youth, the Youth Affairs Agency, a youth academy, aimed at Broad involvement of young people in science, was formed. There are more than 830 non-profit organizations that represent the interests of boys and girls in operation. To discuss issues related to youth in Parliament, to strengthen the special attention of members of Parliament on youth issues, a "youth parliament" is functioning under the legislative chamber and Senate of the House of Commons. This advisory body, which serves as a political platform, will be an important factor for young people to

directly monitor parliamentary activities, involve them in the process of legislative creativity, carry out propaganda and propaganda among young people, solve problems thinking of young people with their own participation, Support Potential Young personnel and prepare them for state civil service, form a sense of

A number of documents are being adopted in order to implement the state policy aimed at young people in a continuous, effective and harmonious way to the requirements of the Times. The state program on implementation in the "year of youth support and strengthening the health of the population" focuses on the attention paid to young people in our country, the conditions created in various spheres of public life, the emergence of their potential and their place in life, in particular, the inclusion of as many young people as possible in higher education, the, a number of activities are established, such as the selection of personnel and their qualification.

Youth public policy remained at the edge of transition processes in a context where, as at the time, democratic transition problems seemed more important. German philosopher J. Habermas wrote that "excessive projects of self-organization of society open their way, ignoring the influence of traditions, the possibilities of organic growth, the availability of resources, ultimately, cannot be multiplied at will". The socio-political activity of young people affects not only the innovation development of society, but also the national security of the state. In the absence of a targeted youth Public Policy, youth political activism can lead to the emigration of the fundamentals of statehood by focusing on national values.

It is known that young people tend to unite around leaders who come out of themselves from a psychological point of view. In political parties, too, the work carried out to identify young captains and prepare them will serve to strengthen the sa - Mara formation of future politicians. While current statistics are looked at, only 1.2% of youth belonging to parti - ya to the territorial, district and city councils and primary organizations of political parties are elected as depu - tat, while in the regional, district and city councils, 1.3% of the youth members are elected as depu-tat.

Looking at foreign experience, it should be noted that unconventional thinking and creativity are appreciated in large educational institutions in Democratic states, namely Harvard (USA), Oxford and Cambridge (UK) universities, the EMLYON Business School (Lyon, France). Students-young people are instructed to develop proposals with specific mechanisms aimed at solving economic and social problems in society. Through this, graduates are constantly recognized by society in politics and business management.

It is also advisable to identify young people who are rich in political characteristics and have a high reputation among the public, prepare them as potential candidates for deputies in elections for local state authorities, and form a "youth quota" for the candidate of people's deputies and deputies to the Legislative Chamber of the Supreme Assembly by political parties.

In this regard, it is possible to expand legal propaganda activities among young people in remote districts, taking into account the fact that in the central regions, youth also have legal information through alternative channels, ensuring that they have a higher legal culture compared to remote districts .

Youth advisory bodies exist in many regions of our country, they operate in the subject under the legislative and executive authorities. Members of youth advisory bodies can carry out

their projects and protect the interests of youth, gain experience for their further activities in public authorities and administrations.

Young people under the age of 30 made up 9% of young people and members of precinct election commissions-17.3% of young people – in the district's election commissions, which were held in 2021. This is another current expression of constant attention and care in our country in terms of protecting the rights and interests of young people, creating the necessary conditions for them to show their potential.

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